

An Application of A Neural Network to Buckling Designs of CFRP Laminated Plates

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Abstract

A fiber orientation angle has an important effect on flexural rigidities and buckling values of CFRP symmetric laminated plates and this angle is one of design variables of CFRP. However, it is hard to determine the correct this values in the case of designing of CFRP symmetric laminated plates having a specific buckling value. This decision becomes, so to speak, an inverse problem. This paper presents an application of a neural network to the buckling design of CFRP symmetric laminated plates and gives the solution of this inverse problem by use of the neural network.

Keywords: Inverse Problem, Buckling Design, Composite Material,
Neural Network, Laminated Plates

1. Introduction

Fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) materials show variable rigidities or strengths according to a fiber volume fraction and a fiber orientation angle and degrees of freedom in design are substantially increased as compared with those of the conventional isotropic materials. Although a problem for determining the fiber volume fraction or the fiber orientation angle of unidirectional CFRP laminates or angle-ply CFRP symmetric laminates having the required elastic moduli becomes an inverse problem, a neural network has been applied for this inverse problem and its effectiveness¹ has already been clarified. In recent years, there have been reported some applications of the neural network to the fields of computational mechanics such as the identification problem for the structure, the monitoring problem of operation of the adaptive structure or the inverse analysis of the contact stress field.

In this report, the neural network is applied to ① a problem obtaining a buckling stress of a square CFRP symmetric laminated plate, ② an inverse problem for obtaining a fiber orientation angle by giving a buckling stress of the square CFRP symmetric laminated plate, ③ a problem obtaining a minimum buckling stress and the number of buckle half wavelength of the CFRP symmetric laminated plate having any size and any fiber orientation angle under any bi-axial compressive resultants ratio and ④ an inverse problem for obtaining a buckling stress of a rectangular CFRP symmetric laminated plate under any bi-

axial compressive resultants ratio. The effectiveness of this method for the buckling design of CFRP laminated plates is demonstrated through the four numerical examples.

2. Neural network

In a neuron model indicated in Fig.1 (hereinafter called as a unit), the lower subscripts i and j ($= 1$ to l) denote a unit number and the upper subscript N ($= 1$ to F) denotes a layer of the hierarchical neural network. Assuming that h_i^N is a threshold of the unit i at the layer N , x_j^{N-1} is an input value from the unit j at the layer $N-1$, and that $W_{ij}^{N,N-1}$ is a connection strength (weight function) of the unit i at the layer N to the other unit j at the layer $N-1$, a state value \bar{x}_i^N of the unit i at the layer N is expressed as

$$\bar{x}_i^N = \sum_{j=1}^l W_{ij}^{N,N-1} x_j^{N-1} - h_i^N \tag{1}$$

and an output value x_i^N of the unit i is calculated by either of the following two equations.

$$x_i^N = f(\bar{x}_i^N) = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-\bar{x}_i^N}} - 1 \tag{2} \quad x_i^N = f(\bar{x}_i^N) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ 1 + \tanh\left(\frac{\bar{x}_i^N}{\mu_0}\right) \right\} \tag{3}$$

In these equations, $f(\bar{x}_i^N)$ and μ_0 are the quasi-linear response function and the gradient of this function. The value of x_i^N is changed from -1 to $+1$ in Eq.(2) and from 0 to 1 in Eq.(3) and the appropriate one is selected according to the each application.

As shown in Fig.2, the hierarchical neural network is composed of the input layer, the intermediate layers and the output layer. When data x_j^1 are given to the input layer, the output value of x_i^N is calculated by Eqs.(1) and (2) in order at the intermediate layers from the input side to the output and the value x_i^F at the output layer can be finally obtained. Using an error back propagation method and the difference between the values x_i^F at the output layer and output tutor data d_i corresponding to input tutor data, a learning signal δ_i^F of the unit i at the output layer is calculated by the following equation,

$$\delta_i^F = (d_i - \bar{x}_i^F) f'(\bar{x}_i^F) \tag{4}$$

in which, $f'(\bar{x}_i^F)$ denotes a differential of the response function. The learning signal δ_i^N of the unit i at the intermediate layers from the output side to the input is calculated by

$$\delta_i^N = f'(\bar{x}_i^N) \sum_{j=1}^J (\delta_j^{N+1} W_{ij}^{N+1,N}) \quad (5)$$

and a modified connection strength $\Delta W_{ij}^{N,N-1}(k+1)$ at $k+1$ iteration is calculated by

$$\Delta W_{ij}^{N,N-1}(k+1) = \eta \delta_i^N x_j^{N-1} + \alpha \Delta W_{ij}^{N,N-1}(k) \quad (6)$$

in which, $\Delta W_{ij}^{N,N-1}(k)$ is the modified one at k iteration, η and α are a learning and a stability constant. After adding the modified connection strength to the previous one, the iterative calculation using the Eqs. (1) and (2) is executed with $\eta=0.25$ and $\alpha=0.9$ up to the scheduled number. That is, after the tutor input data are given to the input layer and the state and output values at the each layer are calculated by Eqs. (1) and (2), the differences of the values at the output layer and the tutor output data according to the tutor input data are reduced through the iterative calculation. This process is called the learning and the neural network is developed through this process.

In next step, other data are given at the input layer of this developed network and the values at the output layer can be also obtained. This process is called the estimating and the inverse problem can be solved through this process.

3. Buckling design of CFRP symmetrical laminated plate

When the length, the width and the thickness of the plate are defined as a , b and h and the fiber orientation angle of CFRP material is also defined as θ , the angle-ply CFRP symmetric laminated plate $(+\theta/-\theta/-\theta/+\theta)_s$ is macroscopically considered as an orthotropic plate. Under the bi-axial compressive resultants of $N_x = \lambda N_{cr}$, $N_y = (1-\lambda)N_{cr}$ in the length and in the width direction, the buckling stress σ_{cr} for the simply supported boundary condition is defined² as

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 \left\{ D_{11} \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^2 \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^4 \right\}}{h \left\{ \lambda \left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^2 + (1-\lambda) \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^2 \right\}} \quad (7)$$

where D_{ij} ($ij=11, 22, 12, 66$) are the flexural stiffnesses, and m and n are the number of buckle half wavelength in the length and the width direction, respectively. Eq. (7) is used to produce the tutor data set (input and output) and to compare with the value at the output layer.

4. Example of application

Material properties of the unidirectional CFRP material used in the buckling

design are the following values, $E_L=157.0\text{GPa}$, $E_T=10.4\text{GPa}$, $G_{LT}=6.95\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{LT}=0.32$. The width b and the thickness h of the CFRP symmetrical laminated plate are 0.2m and 0.001m . The length a is 0.2m (Sections 4.1 and 4.2), 0.4m (Section 4.4) and is varied from 0.1m to 0.4m (Section 4.3).

4.1. Estimation of buckling stress in uniaxial compression

In order to verify that the same buckling stress of the CFRP symmetric laminated plate by Eq.(7) can be also obtained by the neural network, the neural network for estimating the uniaxial buckling stress is shown in Fig.3. Eight units are given to the input layer, the intermediate layer has three layers with 30 units at the each layer and the unit at the output layer is the buckling stress σ_{cr} . Using the 11 tutor data set in which $\sin\theta$, the one of the input tutor data set, is varied from 0.0 to 1.0 for every 0.1 and $n=1$, $m=1$ or 2 , the neural network is trained through the interative calculation of $300,000$ times. In Fig.4, a mark \bullet ($m=1$) and a mark \blacksquare ($m=2$) denote output values (hereinafter called as the learning value) of the neural network according to the input tutor data and additionally a mark \circ ($m=1$) and a mark \square ($m=2$) denote output values (hereinafter called as the estimating value) obtained from this developed the neural network using the other ten input data of $\sin\theta$. The values of $m=1$ (marks \bullet and \circ) and $m=2$ (marks \blacksquare and \square) completely coincide with the analytical ones by Eq.(7) indicated by solid lines. In Fig.5, a summation of square error E obtained from the difference between the tutor output data and the learning values is plotting to the iteration number k . In the case of $m=2$, the shape of the graph shown in Fig.4 is simple, so that the value is converged with a smaller iteration number. However, since the shape of $m=1$ is not simple as that of $m=2$, it is required to execute more iteration.

4.2. Estimation of fiber orientation angle in uniaxial compression

The neural network analyzing an inverse problem of Section 4.1, in which the buckling stress in Fig.3 is replaced with the fiber orientation angle so as to get the fiber orientation angle θ in the output layer is developed with two intermediate layers with 30 units at the each layer. Since m becomes to 1 and the buckling stresses of θ and $(90^\circ-\theta)$ are equal to each other in the case of a square plate, two units at the output layer are set. In this case, the $50,000$ iterations are executed with the seven tutor data set obtained from θ changing from 0.0° to 37.5° for every 7.5° and 44.0° . The Learning values (mark \bullet) and the estimating values (mark \circ) are coincided with analytical values (solid line) in Fig.6. This figure shows that the neural network for estimating the two fiber orientation angles according to one buckling stress is developed and the neural network can be applied for the inverse problem having multi-output

values.

4.3. Estimation of minimum buckling stress and buckle half wave numbers under bi-axial compression

When the aspect ratio a/b of the rectangular plate, the bi-axial compressive resultants ratio λ and the fiber orientation angle θ are varied, obtaining a minimum buckling stresses $\sigma_{cr, min}$ with the number of buckle half wavelength m and n become a forward problem. However, these values may not be easily obtained. In this case, the following neural network is developed. Nine units ($E_L, E_T, G_{LT}, \nu_{LT}, a, b, h, \theta, \lambda$) are given to the input layer, the intermediate layer has two layers with 30 units at the each layer and the output layer has three units of $\sigma_{cr, min}, m$ and n . This neural network are trained by 75 tutor data set and the 20,000 iterations. These data set are calculated by substituting θ, λ and a/b for Eq. (7) with the integer values of m, n . θ has five cases changing from 0.0° to 90.0° for every 22.5° and λ has five cases changing from 0.0 to 1.0 for every 0.25 and a/b has three cases of 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0. Table.1 shows the result of $\theta=0.0^\circ$ as one example of them. The values in the upper part of the table obtained from $\theta=0.0^\circ, \lambda=1.0$ to 0.0 and $a/b=0.5, 1.0$ and 2.0 are all the learning ones. The values in the lower part obtained from the same θ and λ as ones of the upper and $a/b=0.75$ and 1.5 are the estimating ones. Since m and n should be integer, the learning and the estimating values of m and n are rounded and they coincide with the analytical ones. In addition, $\sigma_{cr, min}$ are also coincided with the analytical ones by Eq.(7). Table.2 shows the all estimating values obtained from the this neural network for the other combinations of $\theta, a/b$, and λ . Results of m and n show that only the four cases of ① $\theta=11.25^\circ, a/b=0.75, \lambda=0.125$, ② $\theta=33.75^\circ, a/b=0.75, \lambda=0.125$, ③ $\theta=78.75^\circ, a/b=1.5, \lambda=0.625$ and ④ $\theta=78.75^\circ, a/b=1.5, \lambda=0.375$ (a mark * in the table) are different from their analytical ones. This fact is due to a slight difference of buckling stress by the difference of these m and n . However, the other estimating values of m and n are coincided with the analytical ones. $\sigma_{cr, min}$ are approximately coincided with the analytical ones. The results of λ and a/b for other values of θ are eliminated due to space limitation, however, similar results are obtained. In consequence, the neural network can be developed to obtain the minimum buckling stress with the numbers of buckle half wavelength for any values of combinations of the fiber orientation angle, the aspect ratio and the bi-axial compressive resultants ratio.

4.4. Estimation of bi-axial compressive resultant ratio

As one example of the inverse problem in section 4.3, when the buckling stress of unidirectional laminated plate ($\theta=0.0^\circ$) with the aspect ratio of $a/b=2.0$

under bi-axial compressive resultants λN_{cr} and $(1-\lambda)N_{cr}$ is given, the neural network for estimating λ is developed. Eight units ($E_L, E_T, G_{LT}, \nu_{LT}, a, b, h, \sigma_{cr}$) are given to the input layer, three intermediate layer have 30 units at the each layer and one unit at the output layer is the value of λ . Using 11 tutor data set obtained from the variation of λ from 0.0 to 1.0 for every 0.1, this neural network is trained through the iterative calculation of 300,000. In Fig.7, the learning values (● mark) and the estimating values (○ mark) are approximately coincided with the analytical ones (solid line) and then the neural network can be applied of the inverse problem for estimating the bi-axial compressive resultants ratio.

5. Conclusions

In order to apply the neural network to the buckling design of CFRP symmetric laminated plate, the four cases are considered and their results are compared with analytical ones. The main features obtained through this study are summarized as follows.

- (1) When the material constants of unidirectional CFRP material, the fiber orientation angle of CFRP symmetric laminated plate and its size are given, the same buckling stress as the analytical one can be obtained by the neural network.
- (2) The neural network can be applied for the inverse problem which is hard to solve by the analytical method, i.e. the problem obtaining the bi-axial compressive resultants ratio from the buckling stress.
- (3) The neural network can also be applied to the inverse problem of the multi-output values, i.e. the problem obtaining two fiber orientation angles from one buckling stress.
- (4) In addition, the neural network trained by the limited number of tutor data can be applied for the problem obtaining the numerous minimum buckling stress and the numbers of buckle half wavelength by the generalizing capability of the neural network.

In the future, the authors will try to apply the neural network to the problem for estimating other mechanical properties of CFRP from some mechanical ones or to an identification problem for estimating the defects in composite materials.

References

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Fig.1 Neuron model

Fig.4 Learning and estimating values of buckling stresses under uniaxial compression

Fig.2 Neural network

Fig.3 Neural network for buckling stress under uniaxial compression

Fig.5 Variation of summation of square error and iteration number of learning

Fig.6 Learning and estimating values of fiber orientation angles under uniaxial compression

Fig.7 Learning and estimating values of compressive resultant ratio under bi-axial compression

Table.1 Learning and estimating values of buckling stress and numbers of buckle half wavelength under bi-axial compression ($\theta=0.0^\circ$)

λ	a/b	1.0		0.75		0.5		0.25		0.0	
		Analysis	Network								
Learning	0.5	(1.1)	(1.0.1.1)	(1.2)	(1.0.2.0)	(1.3)	(1.0.2.9)	(1.4)	(1.0.4.0)	(1.4)	(1.0.3.9)
		13.8	13.5	16.7	17.4	14.6	14.8	11.7	11.7	9.5	9.6
	1.0	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.1)	(1.2)	(1.0.2.0)	(1.2)	(1.0.2.0)	(1.2)	(1.0.1.9)
		4.2	4.8	4.2	3.8	3.8	3.6	2.9	3.3	2.4	2.6
	2.0	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)
		2.4	2.7	1.4	1.7	0.9	1.2	0.7	1.0	0.6	0.9
Estimating	0.75	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.3)	(1.2)	(1.0.2.4)	(1.3)	(1.0.3.3)	(1.3)	(1.0.2.9)
		6.6	7.7	7.4	7.8	6.5	7.8	5.4	7.4	4.3	5.5
	1.5	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.1)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.2)
		2.6	3.2	2.0	2.0	1.6	1.3	1.4	1.1	1.2	1.1

(,) denote m and n. Unit of buckling stress is MPa

Table.2 Estimating values of buckling stress and numbers of half wavelength under bi-axial compression

$\theta(^{\circ})$	λ	a/b	0.875		0.625		0.375		0.125	
			Analysis	Network	Analysis	Network	Analysis	Network	Analysis	Network
11.25	0.75	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.2)	(1.0.2.2)	(1.2)*	(1.0.2.9)	
		7.2	8.0	8.2	8.7	7.1	11.2	6.1	9.3	
	1.5	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.1)	
		2.7	3.7	2.2	2.1	1.8	1.4	1.5	1.4	
33.75	0.75	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.0.9)	(1.2)*	(1.0.1.2)	
		8.1	7.8	9.1	9.3	10.5	15.8	12.0	15.7	
	1.5	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	
		5.4	5.9	4.3	5.0	3.5	3.2	3.0	2.2	
56.25	0.75	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	
		6.6	6.3	7.4	7.3	8.5	7.2	10.1	9.8	
	1.5	(2.1)	(2.1.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	
		6.6	7.0	5.7	6.4	4.7	5.1	4.0	3.5	
78.75	0.75	(1.1)	(1.2.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.1.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	
		3.6	3.2	4.1	4.0	4.7	4.9	5.5	6.3	
	1.5	(3.1)	(3.1.1.0)	(2.1)*	(2.6.1.0)	(1.1)*	(1.6.1.0)	(1.1)	(1.0.1.0)	
		3.3	3.6	4.1	4.3	4.6	4.9	3.9	4.0	

(,) denote m and n. Unit of buckling stress is MPa